
The Energy Issue at the focus of the Sustainable Development in Morocco: the links between economic development, energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions and climates

La question énergétique au cœur du développement durable au Maroc : Liens entre développement économique, consommation d'énergie, émissions de Gaz à effet de serre et climats

Auteur 1 : Bikrat Fatiha

Auteur 2 : Karim Mohamed

Bikrat Fatiha¹, (PhD student) EREMEPP,
¹University of Mohammed V, Rabat, Morocco

Karim Mohamed¹, (Professor of higher education) EREMEPP,
¹University of Mohammed V, Rabat, Morocco

Déclaration de divulgation : L'auteur n'a pas connaissance de quelconque financement qui pourrait affecter l'objectivité de cette étude.

Conflit d'intérêts : L'auteur ne signale aucun conflit d'intérêts.

Pour citer cet article : BIKRAT .F & KARIM .M (2022) « La question énergétique au cœur du développement durable au Maroc : Liens entre développement économique, consommation d'énergie, émissions de Gaz à effet de serre et climats », Revue African Scientific Journal, Volume 3, Numéro 13, pp : 218-243.

Date de soumission : Juillet 2022

Date de publication : Août 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7046278

Copyright © 2022 – ASJ

Abstract

This paper focuses on the environment issue that is related to the question of energy and its economic impact. It presents the relevant environmental implications of both energy consumption and economic growth in a global and a national context, and also gives an overview of the important policies and environmental initiatives adopted.

Concerning the empiric study, it consists in the examination of the relationship between energy, environment and economy in the framework of the Kaya identity, which is designed to estimate the CO₂ emissions depending on other factors such as the energy intensity, the index of energy soiling, the population and the gross domestic product per capita.

Keywords: Climate change, sustainable development, energy, Kaya identity, CO₂ emissions

Introduction

The climate change is one of the major challenges facing humanity today. This has led to serious concerns about its origins and its consequences. Scientists have affirmed that the increase in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions has produced a massive accumulated greenhouse gas (GHG), which is responsible for the recent warm temperatures (IPCC, 1995; Watson et al., 1996). Consequently, an important international initiative was launched to reach a collective agreement to contain the increase in global CO₂ emissions. The historical Kyoto Protocol was concluded in 1997, which required developed countries to reduce their annual carbon emissions to an average of 5.2% below 1990 levels (Meclot & Madet, 1997).

Accordingly, Morocco, in line with the necessity to advance on a trajectory of a emissions compatible with the Paris Accord's target of limiting global warming to 2°C or even 1.5°C, has joined the measures agreed at the global level, mainly in the Frame Convention of the United Nations on Climate Change (UNFCCC). The country has adopted numerous sectorial strategies that integrate the environmental dimension in several key economic fields, as energy, transport, agriculture, industry and tourism. This commitment is also expressed in the National Climate Plan (NCP) and the National Strategy for Sustainable Development (NSSD) up to 2030 through the two principal aspects of mitigation and adaptation.

The economic growth is closely linked to the consumption of energy, because high economic performance requires a sufficiently consistent use of energy (Antonakakis et al., 2017). Nevertheless, energy is defined as the prime factor in GHG and impacts on the environment on a short- and long-term basis, subsequently affecting the well-being of the coming generations. Our article focuses on the study of the relationship between economic growth and environmental risks through the consideration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (Wasti & Zaidi, 2020). The examination of the relationship will proceed within the Kaya Identity framework, which allows for the consideration of the energy aspect through econometric methods, introducing other explanatory variables for the study period from 1990 to 2018. The application of the Kaya identity makes it possible to highlight other factors that could impact on the quality of the environment. It concerns population, income per capita, energy intensity of GDP and CO₂ intensity of energy.

The objective of this paper is therefore to estimate, for the case of Morocco, the elasticities of CO₂ emissions with respect to the energy intensity of the economy, the greenhouse gas content of energy, per capita income and population over the period 1990- 2018. The results will help to identify and understand the main factors impacting on environmental quality. They will also

contribute to the orientation and formulation of targeted measures to minimize the impacts of climate change and strengthen the resilience of the economy and ecosystems to continue towards sustainable growth.

In order to provide answers to these questions, our article is structured in three axes: the first axis presents the trends of GHG emissions worldwide and Morocco. The second axis consists of a literature review about the relationship between CO₂ emissions and explanatory variables. The third axis presents the results of the empiric study. The document concludes with some considerations on policy implications.

1. Trends and projections of greenhouse gas emissions worldwide and Morocco

The objective of this section is to give an overview on the evolution of GHG emissions as well as the key sources of these emissions in order to understand why climate mitigation measures are relevant.

1.1. The evolution of the greenhouse gas emissions worldwide

The GHG emissions due to human activities are equivalent to 55.3 billion tonnes of CO₂ in 2018, in which carbon dioxide accounts for the main part, with almost 34 billion tonnes of carbon dioxide emitted worldwide as illustrated in the figure hereafter.

Figure N°1: Evolution of CO₂ emissions in the world from 1990 to 2018
(In billions of tons of CO₂)

Source: Data from the IEA

The global CO₂ emissions have increased by 1.9% in 2018, significantly higher than the previous year (+1.2%). More than 50% of this growth was due to rising emissions in Asia. They are also increasing in Northern America (+2.2%), while the European Union is slowing down (-1.9%).

The Figure N°2, here below, presents the distribution of GHG emissions among the principal emitters: China (29%), the United States (15%), the European Union (11%), India (6%), Russia (5%), Japan (4%), and the rest of the world (30%). The majority of the expected growth in greenhouse gas emissions comes from rapidly emerging countries such as China and India. China surpasses the US as the top emitter in 2018.

The classification of carbon emissions by region reveals only one side of the story. The issue of CO₂ emissions is represented more accurately by its population. That is to say, the total CO₂

emissions are divided by the population of the given region to calculate the per capita data. This is based on the same method of measuring the amount of CO₂ attributed to each individual. This way, countries such as China (the world's largest CO₂ producer) ranks at 52nd in the world with 7 tCO₂ per capita, India is ranked 133rd with only 1.8 tCO₂ per capita and the United States, in 11th position, produces 16 tCO₂ per capita.

The highest rates are concentrated in the gulf countries, such as Qatar (40 tCO₂), Kuwait (34 tCO₂ per capita) or the United Arab Emirates (22 tCO₂ per capita).

Figure N°2 : Global CO₂ emissions by the main emitters in 2018 (in %)

Source: Emissions database for global atmospheric research (EDGAR)

1.1. Trend of total greenhouse gas emissions in Morocco

In the case of Morocco, the emissions of GHG other than CO₂ are little documented. However, the data available allow us at least to conclude that the majority of the GHG emitted has been constituted by the CO₂ emissions observed since 1990 (see Fig N°3). These represented 74.3% in 2010 and 70% in 2016 of Morocco's total GHG emissions.

Figure N° 3: Trend of total GHG emissions in Morocco (Mt of CO₂-equivalent)

Source: EDGAR

Concerning Morocco, the GHG emissions other than CO₂ are little documented. However, the available data allow us to conclude that CO₂ emissions have constituted the greater part of GHGs emitted since 1990 (Fig. 4). They represented 74.3% in 2010 and 70% in 2016 of total GHG emissions in the country.

In 2016, the GHG emissions due to use of energy were dominated by CO₂ emissions with almost 97.6% of the total emissions, i.e. 25.475 MTECO₂. While CH₄ and N₂O emissions represented small percentages with respectively 1.17% and 1.23% of total energy sector emissions.

Figure N°4: Distribution of GHGs emitted by Morocco for the years 1990, 2010 & 2016

Source : Data from the IEA & MEME¹

¹ Résultats de l'inventaire national des émissions marocaines de gaz à effet de serre depuis 1990 (Département de l'Environnement (MEME))

1.2. The evolution of carbon dioxide emissions in Morocco

The analysis of Morocco's historical emissions of CO₂ reveals the following observations: CO₂ emissions have had an increasing trend during the period 1990-2018 (Fig.IV.4). They reached 19.7 million tonnes of CO₂ (MtCO₂) in 1990 and have continuously been rising to attain 58.9 MtCO₂ in 2018. Nevertheless, a comparative study of CO₂ emissions per capita shows that Morocco remains a low emitter of these emissions compared to other Mediterranean countries such as Tunisia and Spain as well as other countries such as the United States and China.

Figure N°5: Trend of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in Morocco (Mt)

Source: Data from the IEA

1.3. Evolution of CO₂ emissions per energy source

The consumption of oil remains the primary source of CO₂ emissions (Figure N°6). It represents 57% of total emissions in 2019, followed by coal 40% and by natural gas with 3.1%. However, emissions generated by coal have slightly decreased since 2010, and recorded a strong growth rate between 2011 and 2015.

Figure N°6: CO₂ emissions by type of combustible in Morocco, 1990-2018 in MteCO₂

Source: Data from the IEA

1.4. Policy Responses to Climate Change

Climate change requires a collective effort and action from all parties including governments, organizations, shareholders and individuals to adapt and implement measures to mitigate the effects of climate change. As carbon dioxide emissions are the major factor causing global warming, any policy response has to focus on effective reduction of these emissions.

1.4.1. The international initiatives for sustainable development

The commitment of the international community to the issue of climate change has been established through several adopted decisions and policies related to GHG emissions limitation and the strengthening of environmental resilience.

Since the adoption and ratification of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the Conference Parties have constantly alerted on the need to enhance efforts for the reduction of GHG emissions and supporting the adaptation of the country's most vulnerable to climate change. All under the principle of "shared but differentiated responsibility".

The challenge of climate change has also been reinforced by the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (adopted in September 2015). The agenda dedicated goal (SDG N°13) to promote the consolidation of efforts through targeted actions and associates climate change to a common cause: transforming the world through an inclusive approach combining the eradication of poverty; promoting economic and social growth and preventing the planetary environment.

These diverse dynamics led towards the adoption of the Paris Agreement (PA), concluded at COP21 and effective as of 4 November 2016. The PA represents a historic step that commit 197 states to stabilize global warming "well below 2°C" by 2100 compared to the temperature of the pre-industrial era (reference period 1861-1880) and to continue efforts to limit this warming to 1.5°C².

1.4.2. The commitment of Morocco to sustainable development and climate change

Morocco, as well as many developing countries, is highly affected by the risks of climate change and is already experiencing the impacts at the national level. In this regard, that Morocco is in complete alignment with international climate change framework obligations. It has signed and ratified the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), adopted in 1992, as well as the Kyoto Protocol stemming from it.

²IPCC (2018) Global Warming of 1.5°C. <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>

These different commitments place it in a position of common obligations to the Convention's Parties. The UNFCCC and the Kyoto Protocol both require signatories to integrate climate change considerations into their national, social, economic and environmental policies and programmes, and to monitor GHG emission levels by promoting the implementation of sustainable practices for the use of carbon capture sinks (forests and others). Finally, it is important to note that both are legally binding commitments that drive and shape countries' attention to the issue of climate change.

The principal basis of Morocco's vision for managing climate change is reflected in the Constitution through the terms of Articles 31, 35 and 88. The second is the international and regional reference framework and subsequent agreements to which Morocco has subscribed. A series of instruments have been developed to implement Morocco's international commitments in respect of climate change: the policy on climate change represents the operational framework for the implementation of a mid and long-term strategy to respond proactively and ambitiously to the challenges raised by climate change.

In order to achieve the national energy strategy objectives, the Climate Change Policy of Morocco (CCPM) has been introduced as a coordination instrument that capitalizes on the several sectorial programs set up to effectively face climate change. It is based on two main components: a mitigation component and an adaptation component. The measures established in the mitigation component are based on two main lines of action, which are promoting renewable energy and saving energy through energy efficiency measures. In the mitigation target that was recently announced by Morocco, an unconditional GHG reduction of 18.3% compared to its "business as usual" (BAU) baseline scenario and a conditional reduction target of 45.5% in the case of receiving an additional \$21.5 billion in support.

The adaptation component of the PCCM involves the introduction of measures designed to reduce vulnerabilities of Morocco's economic sectors, populations and natural environments. It is also important to mention that the estimated cost is very high, at around 40 billion dollars over the next 10 years, or 35% of the country's GDP in 2020. The adaptation of Morocco is provided details in its NDC. More efforts were then made through the elaboration of national communications, the institutionalization of the national GHG inventory system, sectoral analyses and initiatives in order to establish the appropriate framework for Morocco's decarbonization.

2. Theoretical and empirical literature review of the relationship between energy, environment and economy

The first environment concerns were raised by the physiocrats and classical economists, limiting the notion of nature to the land. However, from the end of the Second World War, there emerged a real awareness of the importance of the environmental dimension in economic analysis. In fact, it was the negative impacts on the environment that justified the holding of many international meetings with a view to finding appropriate solutions. The answer that seemed adequate was sustainable development, which considers ecology, economy and society as three inseparable dimensions. In this sense, sustainable development brings a new vision of economic development that ensures economic growth without harming the environment and the ecosystem. Recently, a series of studies and research studies have focused on the link between environmental issues, economic growth and energy consumption. Indeed, the threat of climate change due mainly to emissions of pollutants (CO₂) has drawn attention to the link between economic growth and CO₂ emissions.

Several approaches have been used to study the relationship between economic development, pollutant emissions and energy consumption, mainly: elasticity functions, the Kuznets Environment Curve (KEC), carbon intensity, Kaya Identity, etc.

2.1. The Kuznets Environment Curve (KEC)

An extensive literature has explored the direction of causality between economic growth and pollution, and this has resulted in the hypothesis of the " Kuznets Environment Curve " (KEC), which postulates that the level of environmental degradation increases with economic growth, but at a certain threshold it starts to decline. This conception is made by analogy with the works of Kuznets (Kuznets, 1965) that treat the relationship between inequalities of revenue and the growth level of a determined country.

The Kuznets environmental curve (Fig N°7) is based on a theory proposed by neoclassical economists such as (Grossman & Krueger, 1991), (Shafik & Bandyopadhyay, 1992) and (Selden & Song, 1994) in order to seek answers to the environmental issues. It consists of an inverse U relationship between economic development and environmental pollutants. The hypothesis behind this curve is that, from a development threshold, called the reflection point, the emissions increase with the increase in income (GDP per capita), and then decrease again. This is because the growth in GDP demands more consumption of resources and emits more polluting emissions. However, according to the KEC, a good business can invest a part of its

wealth in the research and development of greener technologies and consequently reduce emissions while still maintaining a growing GDP.

The KEC proceeds through three phases: In the first phase (increasing pollution), economic growth increases environmental degradation until it reaches a pollution peak in the second phase (inflection point) and then reaches the phase of reduced pollution, characterized by a diminution of the environmental impact of growth with increasing per capita income. Otherwise, from a certain threshold, the more the income (standard of living) increases, the more informed consumers are and the more they respect the environment for industrialized and developed countries. This concept has inspired a number of economists to examine if economic growth is accompanied by environmental degradation, by analyzing the relationship between environmental indicators and economic growth indicators. Indeed, several empirical studies have been attempted at linking environmental quality with economic growth. We can rightly mention (Grossman & Krueger, 1995), (Shafik & Bandyopadhyay, 1992), (Cropper & Griffith, 1994), (Selden & Song, 1994), (Antle & Heidebrink, 1995) and (Holtz-Eakin & Selden, 1995).

Figure N°7 : The Kuznets Environment Curve (KEC)

Source : Economic growth and the environment, (Panayotou, 2016)

2.2. Carbon intensity

Energy consumption and carbon intensity are considered the main variables to explain CO₂ emissions. Thus, carbon intensity is the ratio of energy-related CO₂ emissions to economic growth. The analysis of the evolution of CO₂ intensity (Fig. N°8) reveals an increasingly important trend between 1990 and 1995. Also, an improvement in energy intensity was observed over the whole period from 2005 to 2015, this was driven in part by the introduction

of liquefied natural gas (LNG)³ in the national energy mix. However, there is a return to an increasing rate of carbon intensity from 2015 onwards.

Figure N°8: CO₂ emissions per unit of GDP (kg CO₂/2015 USD), Morocco 1990-2018

Source: Data from the IAE

2.3. The Kaya identity

The KEC has been criticized by (Dinda, 2004) because according to this curve emissions are a part of GDP, and so it assumes a unidirectional causal relationship from GDP to emissions, but the reverse may exist. However, this curve does not highlight the other factors affecting the emissions level other than economic growth. A relevant proposal for reflection is provided by an equation that need to be used: it is the so-called "Kaya equation", which is essential for any discussion of the climate and humanity's impact on it. *So what can Kaya provide about the planet's future?*

The famous equation is named from the Japanese economist Yoichi Kaya who proposed this representation in his work Environment, Energy, and Economy : strategies for sustainability (Kaya & Yokobori, 1997). This equation illustrates and relates the influence and impact of human activities on greenhouse gas emissions.

For this purpose, the Kaya identity proposes a decomposition of CO₂ emissions according to different economic, demographic, industrial and political parameters.

$$CO_2 \text{ emissions from fossil fuel consumption} = \text{Population} * \text{GDP per capita} * \text{Energy intensity of growth} * \text{Carbon intensity of energy} \quad (1)$$

³ [La stratégie de développement du gaz naturel liquéfié dévoilée \(lematin.ma\)](http://lematin.ma)

If we are thinking of emissions in terms of growth rates, the Kaya identity is expressed as a comparison between the growth rate of emissions and the total growth rate of the four components mentioned above.

(IPCC, 2007) has estimated that the 1.9% annual growth in global CO₂ emissions from 1970 to 2004 is explained by an annual population growth of 1.6%, an annual growth in GDP per capita of 1.8%, an annual decrease in energy intensity of 1.2% and a decrease in carbon intensity of 0.2%. In other words, progress in energy efficiency and the "decarbonization" of energy use has not been sufficient to offset the population and income per capita expansion. The most common form is based on the following theoretical specification:

$$CO_2 = \frac{CO_2}{Energy} * \frac{Energy}{GDP} * \frac{GDP}{Population} * Population \quad (2)$$

It is then simple to list these factors, starting by the carbon content of a unit of energy, followed by the quantity of energy used to create a unit of money, then by the per capita income and finally by the number of population. All of these factors and their evolutions will be simulated in an interactive model so as to determine the long-term trends in terms of carbon emissions.

This equation stipulates that population, economic growth and technology (that means: energy and CO₂ intensities) are the determinants of greenhouse gas emissions. In other words, any increase or decrease in the quantity of CO₂ emissions is to be accompanied by an equivalent change in at least one of the decomposition factors. The combined effect of these factors on the environment can be detailed in the next paragraphs.

2.3.1 Effect of population growth on the environment

The population size and its growth are the most important factors responsible for the carbon emissions. The causal schema derived from this relationship indicates that, firstly, a large population could implicate an additional energy demand for industry and transport, causing significant emissions. In the second place, an increase in population contributes to GHG through its impact on the deforestation. An increase in population causes more deforestation, changes in land use and more consumption of wood for fuel. Thus, the larger the population, the higher the CO₂ emissions, which contribute to the greenhouse effect (Birdsall, 1992). (Shi, 2003) has demonstrated that an increase of 1% in population generates an additional 1.28% of GHG emissions on average. (Dyson, 2015) forecasts that the growth of the world's population (estimated at 9 billion in 2050) will lead to a 27% rise in CO₂ emissions, which is considered by scientists to be the direct cause of global warming, compared to a 400% increase between 1950 and 2000.

2.3.2. Effect of the economic development on environment

The correlation between economic development and CO₂ emissions has been demonstrated by several studies (Luukkanen & Kaivo-Oja, 2002), (Arouri et al., 2012), (Antonakakis et al., 2017) (Saboori et al., 2012) et (Gorus & Aydin, 2019). Economic development is accompanied by an increase in the consumption of fossil fuels, with increasing the amount of coal, oil and natural gas being consumed by factories and electric stations, by motor vehicles and by domestic households. As a result, carbon dioxide emissions have become the primary source of greenhouse gases. The international experience has proven that air quality in most countries deteriorates in the early stages of the industrialization and urbanization process. But as their income advances, the national priorities change: they realize the precious value of their natural resources (clean air, clean water, fertile arable land, abundant forests), then they adopt and enforce laws to protect them.

2.3.3. Impact of technology on the environment

The majority of studies have revealed that a policy to combat climate change will positively impact on employment, for example in the field of renewable energy or advanced technologies. Technological solutions that allow for reduced consumption levels and significantly decreased pollutants (low carbon intensity) are likely to lead to the development of more advanced technologies, such as new combustion methods (Adenle, 2020).

All three factors, population, wealth and technology, are correlated in equation (2) that will serve as a basis for assessing their effects on the carbon emissions in Morocco. Because this equation is not easily estimable, we adopt an additive stochastic form defined by:

$$\ln CO_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \ln \frac{CO_2}{Energy} + \beta_2 \cdot \ln \frac{Energy}{GDP} + \beta_3 \cdot \ln \frac{GDP}{Population} + \beta_4 \cdot \ln Population + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

Where \ln : the neperian logarithm; $\varepsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$

3. The empirical study of the Relationship between Energy, Environment and Economy: Case of Morocco

The relationship between economic activities, energy and environmental risks remains an open question. To take these risks into account, following previous studies, we use cointegration to examine this relationship between energy consumption, CO₂ emissions and economic growth in the same equation within the Kaya identity to estimate the quantity of CO₂ emissions as a function of other factors including the energy intensity, the index of energy salinity, the population and the gross domestic product per capita.

3. Econometric strategy

Studying the existence of a long-term equilibrium between the variables we are considering requires a well-defined econometric approach. Indeed, a crucial step consists in checking the stationarity of the variables by using unit root tests. Once the order of integration of the series is determined, the existence of a long term equilibrium relationship is tested using the Engle and Granger cointegration test in this case.

3.1.1. Specification of the econometric model

The specification of the model is inspired from the " Kaya identity " introduced in the previous section. In order to estimate equation (3), it is proposed to evaluate the elasticities of CO₂ emissions in both the long and short term. In the long run, they give an indication of the decarbonisation trend (trend in CO₂ intensities in relation to economic growth). In the short term, they evaluate, using an error correction model (ECM), the shocks caused by each factor on the real trajectory of GHG intensities (variations around the trend). This approach implies that the order of integration of the variables must first be studied.

3.1.2. Data analysis

This section presents the different variables to be used in order to study the evolution of CO₂ emissions as a function of economic growth, energy and population for Morocco. Thus, the variables to be considered are those specified in equation (3) of the Kaya identity, which are: CO₂ emissions, index of energy salinity, energy intensity, income and population. The data is annual and covered the period from 1990 to 2018 downloaded mainly from the International Energy Agency website.

CO₂ emissions

CO₂ is responsible for about 70% of GHG, and is produced especially by the combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation and industrial combustion...etc. In this study, we use CO₂ emissions, measured in metric tons, as an environmental variable. The evolution of CO₂ emissions, as presented above, shows an upward trend from 39.680 mtCO₂ in 1990 to the highest level of emissions in 2018 with 94.290 mtCO₂.

Index of energy soiling

This concerns CO₂ emissions in relation to economic growth. The index of energy soiling is defined as the quantity of CO₂ emitted by each unit of energy.

$$ISE = \frac{CO_2}{Energy} \quad (4)$$

The evolution of the energy soiling index is characterised by fluctuations throughout the period 1990-2018. The index showed an upward trend until 1995. However, the period from 1996 to

2000 revealed instability in the ESI. It reached a peak in 2002, at 88.9 tonnes of CO₂ per ktoe. From 2003 onwards, this index experienced a remarkable decrease thanks to environmental policies adapted to reduce CO₂ emissions as part of the efforts to combat climate change, in particular the introduction of the use of natural gas in the production of electricity at the level of combined cycle thermal power stations. However, the ISE is resuming its upward trend until 2018.

Figure N° 9: Evolution of the Index of Energy Soiling (IES) in Tco₂/ktep, period 1990 - 2018

Source: Data from the IAE

Energy intensity

The energy intensity is the ratio between energy consumption and an indicator of economic activity measured in monetary units at constant prices. It represents the amount of energy required to produce one unit of GDP.

$$IE = \frac{\text{Energy}}{\text{GDP}} \quad (5)$$

In the overall picture, the evolution of energy intensity during the period from 1990 to 2015 registered fluctuations ranging from 0.19 toe/\$1000 of GDP to 0.23 toe/\$1000 of GDP. Starting in 2016, the EI experienced a significant decrease until 2018.

Figure N°10: Evolution of the Energy Intensity (EI) in toe/k of dollars, period 1990-2018

Source: Data from the IAE

GDP per capita

GDP per capita is an indicator of economic activity used in our case to measure the development of a country. This indicator has continuously increased over the entire study period. This increase reflects the growth in the comfort needs of the Moroccan population driven by the significant improvement in its living conditions.

Figure N°11: Evolution of GDP per capita in Morocco (USD), 1990-2018

Source : Data from the Word Bank⁴

Population

As its name indicates, it refers to the number of inhabitants, in millions. Population in Morocco has increased from 24.8 million in 1990 to over 36 million in 2018, an increase of 45% over this period. Approximately 64% of the country's inhabitants live in large cities. The tendency for urbanization is increasing by 2.0% per year.

⁴ <https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/>

Figure N°12: Evolution of the Moroccan population, 1990-2018

Source: Data from the World Bank and HCP

3.1.3. Order of integration

As the first step in the empirical analysis, we need to examine if the time series have unit roots. A good specification of regression models requires that all of the variables are integrated in the same order as to avoid the presence of spurious regression problems. This is why it is important to apply stationarity tests. These are used to check whether a time series is stable over time, considering that a relatively invariant series is useful for forecasting.

For the stationarity tests of the series presented in the previous subsection, we adopted the unit root tests proposed by (Ng & Perron, 2001). Such tests are most robust because of their high levels and power characteristics, particularly for residual distortions in a negative serial correlation. The unit root tests were conducted on the log-linearised series. The results of these tests are provided in the next table:

Table N°1: Unit tests root

Variables		Test Ng-Perron			
		MZa	MZt	MSB	MPT
Statistique du test					
Ln co ₂		-1,63	-0.63791	0.39152	10.8938
Ln co ₂ /énergie		-10.52	-2.21409	0.21042	2.63065
Ln enr/pib		-7.54	-1.83967	0.24388	3.60837
Ln pib/hab		0.63	0.54317	0.86021	49.3325
Ln pop		-3.36	-1.01944	0.30314	7.08423
critical value	1%	-13.8	-2.58	0.174	1.78
	5%	-8.1	-1.98	0.233	3.17
	10%	-5.7	-1.62	0.275	4.45

Source: Authors

The statistics of the MZa test as well as the other statistics of Ng and Perron are higher than the Critical Values at the 1%, 5% and 10% thresholds, so the null hypothesis is accepted, the considered series have unit roots, and are non-stationary.

By using the sequential strategy of the ADF test, results demonstrated that series in difference are stationary and consequently are integrated of order 1. Accordingly, we can pass to next step and test the existence of long term equilibrium relationship between LCO₂, LISE, LIE, LREV and LPOP.

3.1.4. Co-integration test

We have seen in the previous part of this document that one of the approaches of the cointegration theory is the two-step method proposed by (Engle & Granger, 1987). The adoption of this method is motivated by the fact that the dependent variable is known in advance and is based on the Kaya identity where CO₂ emissions are related to the index of energy soiling, energy intensity, gross domestic product per capita and population. The first step consists in showing that there exists a long term relationship between a dependent variable and explicative variables, then the second step is to express these cointegrated variables in an error correction model, which estimation allows to determine the short-term adjustments.

An additional cointegration approach is the Maximum Likelihood Method, suggested by (Johansen, 1988) and (Johansen & Juselius, 1990)), which offers the advantage of being a multivariate approach. It permits the differentiation of several cointegrating vectors and their estimation by introducing a dynamic adjustment.

Since we dispose of a theoretic order between variables a priori, we choose the Univariate method of Engle and Granger (1987) in this study. In the Engle and Granger approach, cointegration is tested by performing a unit root test on the residues of the cointegrating equation. Concretely, the first step is to estimate the long-term relationship (3).

We note by $\Delta\hat{\varepsilon}_t$ the residue of estimation. In the second stage, we apply the Dickey-Fuller test to this residue:

$$\Delta\hat{\varepsilon}_t = \varphi_1^*\hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1} + \Delta\varphi_2^*\hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1} + \Delta\varphi_3^*\hat{\varepsilon}_{t-1} + \dots + \vartheta_t \quad (6)$$

Si:

$\varphi_1^* = 0$: The serie $\hat{\varepsilon}_t$ has one unit root and two variables are not cointegrated.

$\varphi_1^* < 0$: The serie $\hat{\varepsilon}_t$ is stationary and the cointegration hypothesis is accepted.

Thus, the estimation gave us the following long-run relationship:

$$\ln CO_2 = -42.004 + 0,4359 \times \ln \frac{CO_2}{Energy} + 0,4045 \times \ln \frac{Energy}{GDP} + 0,214 \times \ln \frac{GDP}{Population} + 2,4776 \times \ln Population \quad (7)$$

The ADF test statistic on the residuals is equal to -3.65. It is inferior to the tabulated value (-2.97) at 5%, so the hypothesis of stationarity of the residuals is accepted and consequently, we can

conclude that there is a long term equilibrium relationship between the variables considered. All elasticities are statistically significant at the 1% level and have the expected sign. We therefore conclude that over the long term:

- ❖ A 1% of increase in the index of energy soiling generates a 0.43% of increase in CO2 emissions;
- ❖ A 1% of increase in energy intensity causes a 0.4% increase in emissions.
- ❖ The elasticity of the income is estimated at 0.2%, which suggests that the emissions increase at a rhythm lower than the economic growth.
- ❖ The contribution of the population to accelerating CO2 emissions is however very significant, amounting to 2.47%.

3.2. The error correction model

Accepting the cointegration means to admit the existence of a stationary state relation between any two series of variables with a common tendency to follow in the same trend. Any temporary deviation from this equilibrium is treated as aleatory.

Following the representation theorem of Granger, any cointegrated system implies the existence of an error-correcting mechanism that prevents the variables from diverging too much from their long-term equilibrium. While cointegration allows to specify the existence and type of divergences between two series theoretically connected and to model the performance of these variables, on the other hand, the error correction model helps to explain and deduce the error correction mechanism.

In a general way, the estimation of the error correction model is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta LCO2_t = & 0.007442 + 0.449943 \times \Delta LCO2_ENR_t + 0.345037 \times \\ & \Delta LENR_GDP_t + 0.154731 \times \Delta LPIB_Inhabitant_t + 2.018993 \times \\ & \Delta LENR_GDP_t - 0.658154 \times Z_{t-1} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Where Z_{t-1} is the error correction term from the estimation of the cointegrating relationship.

The estimation of the model indicates that in short term the elasticities are statistically significant. The index of energy soiling is elastic in both the short and long term. By contrast, CO₂ emissions increase more proportionally in the short than the long term as a reaction to an increase of energy intensity. In addition, the income elasticity is more pronounced in the long term than in the short term. And finally, we also note that a 1% increase in population leads to a 2.01% increase in CO₂ emissions in the short term. To contain this exponential increase, the development of capacities and competences in the field of eco-friendly energies, renewable

energies and more in general a sustainable development technology, offers promising and exciting activities for the new generations.

Moreover, the parameter of the error correction term is negative and significant, confirming the existence of a long term relationship between CO₂ emission and other considered variables. The parameter value indicates that, in the case of short-term disequilibrium, the CO₂ emission returns quickly to its equilibrium path (the convergence speed is estimated at 65.81%).

This econometric study has therefore made it possible to see that, over the period 1990-2018, the variables set explained the CO₂ emission in Morocco in a very satisfactory and consistent way. Moreover, the analysis of the impulsive response functions (see Fig. N°13) illustrates that, in the long term, the energy intensity, the index of energy soiling and the per capita income have a relevant incidence on the reduction of CO₂ emissions. The projections to 2030 indicate that the gain in energy intensity is enhanced but the trend in CO₂ emissions is increasing.

These relatively high elastic values suggest that policy measures acting on energy and "carbon" intensities would be effective in reducing CO₂ emissions, particularly in the industrial sector.

In the same perspective, regulatory measures (in the form of instructions given to companies and households) or the introduction of a carbon tax could also reduce fossil fuel consumption.

We will remind here of a number of decisions that highlight the efforts made in this regard, among the most significant ones:

- ❖ Concerning the rational use of energy in energy-intensive sectors (transport, buildings and industry): Increase the financial support for the promotion of energy management in the context of energy audits and the monitoring of programme contracts;
- ❖ About electricity savings: Adopt standards corresponding to limited energy consumption thresholds for household appliances considered to be the most energy-intensive (air conditioner, refrigerator, electric oven, iron).
- ❖ Regarding renewable energies:
 - Obligation of using solar water heaters in new public buildings;
 - Optimisation of the use of photovoltaic solar energy in the different sectors;
 - Developing the use of wind energy for electricity production.
- ❖ On the substitution by natural gas: Increase the contribution of natural gas in the final energy consumption in the different sectors of activity: residential, tertiary and industrial.

Figure N° 13: Impulsive response functions 2010-2030

Source: Authors

Conclusion

As a country emitting low levels of greenhouse gases, Morocco is nevertheless vulnerable to the effects of climate change and has taken up the challenges of the global climatic agenda. It has launched a new model of development that respects both human and natural resources, by initiating a transition to sustainable and resilient economic growth. The Moroccan transition is taking place today through important structural projects.

In this context, reducing GHG constitutes a top priority for Morocco. It will be necessary to develop appropriate models allowing a clear understanding and forecasting of future trends.

For this purpose, with the help of a Kaya-type equation, we have estimated the short and long term elasticities of several variables influencing the emissions of CO₂. The indicators are carbon intensity per unit of energy, energy intensity, per capita income and population.

From the obtained estimation, it appears that the elasticities are significant and are higher in the long term. These results are corroborated by the analysis of impulse response functions, which also revealed that in the long term: energy intensity, the index of energy soiling and, to a certain degree, per capita income have a decisive influence on the reduction of GHG emissions.

Consequently, actions focusing on these factors, in combination with other measures, should undoubtedly contribute to future greenhouse gas reductions. The dissemination of successful practical experiences in similar contexts is also of major importance for raising the awareness of all actors.

References:

- (1) Adenle, A. A. (2020). Assessment of solar energy technologies in Africa-opportunities and challenges in meeting the 2030 agenda and sustainable development goals. *Energy Policy*, 137, 111180.
- (2) Antle, J. M., & Heidebrink, G. (1995). Environment and development: theory and international evidence. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 43(3), 603–625.
- (3) Antonakakis, N., Chatziantoniou, I., & Filis, G. (2017). Energy consumption, CO2 emissions, and economic growth: An ethical dilemma. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 68, 808–824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.09.105>
- (4) Arouri, M. E. H., Youssef, A. Ben, M'henni, H., & Rault, C. (2012). Energy consumption, economic growth and CO2 emissions in Middle East and North African countries. *Energy Policy*, 45, 342–349.
- (5) Birdsall, N. (1992). *Another look at population and global warming* (Vol. 1020). World Bank Publications.
- (6) Cropper, M., & Griffith, C. (1994). In search of an environmental Kuznets curve in sulphur dioxide concentrations: a Bayesian model averaging approach'. *American Economic Review*, 84, 250–254.
- (7) Dinda, S. (2004). Environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis: a survey. *Ecological Economics*, 49(4), 431–455.
- (8) Dyson, T. (2015). *Population Dynamics and Sustainable Development*. April.
- (9) Engle, R. F., & Granger, C. W. J. (1987). Co-integration and error correction: representation, estimation, and testing. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 251–276.
- (10) Gorus, M. S., & Aydin, M. (2019). The relationship between energy consumption, economic growth, and CO2 emission in MENA countries: causality analysis in the frequency domain. *Energy*, 168, 815–822.
- (11) Grossman, G. M., & Krueger, A. B. (1991). *Environmental impacts of a North American free trade agreement*. National Bureau of economic research Cambridge, Mass., USA.
- (12) Grossman, G. M., & Krueger, A. B. (1995). Economic growth and the environment. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 110(2), 353–377.
- (13) Holtz-Eakin, D., & Selden, T. M. (1995). Stoking the fires? CO2 emissions and economic growth. *Journal of Public Economics*, 57(1), 85–101.
- (14) IPCC. (1995). IPCC Second Assessment. *A Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on*

Climate Change, WMO-UNEP.

- (15) IPCC. (2007). Climate change, the physical science basis. *Agu Fall Meeting Abstracts, 2007*, U43D-01.
- (16) Johansen, S. (1988). Statistical analysis of cointegration vectors. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 12(2–3), 231–254.
- (17) Johansen, S., & Juselius, K. (1990). Maximum likelihood estimation and inference on cointegration—with applications to the demand for money. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 52(2), 169–210.
- (18) Kaya, Y., & Yokobori, K. (1997). *Environment, energy, and economy: strategies for sustainability*. United Nations University Press Tokyo.
- (19) Kuznets, S. S. (1965). *Economic growth and structure: selected essays*.
- (20) Luukkanen, J., & Kaivo-Oja, J. (2002). Meaningful participation in global climate policy? Comparative analysis of the energy and CO₂ efficiency dynamics of key developing countries. *Global Environmental Change*, 12(2), 117–126.
- (21) Meclot, B., & Madet, D. (1997). *Climatic change. The third Conference of the Parties of the United Nations-Framework Convention. Kyoto, Japan, 1-10 December 1997*. Electricite de France (EDF).
- (22) Ng, S., & Perron, P. (2001). Lag length selection and the construction of unit root tests with good size and power. *Econometrica*, 69(6), 1519–1554.
- (23) Panayotou, T. (2016). Economic growth and the environment. *The Environment in Anthropology*, 24, 140–148.
- (24) Saboori, B., Sulaiman, J., & Mohd, S. (2012). Economic growth and CO₂ emissions in Malaysia: a cointegration analysis of the environmental Kuznets curve. *Energy Policy*, 51, 184–191.
- (25) Selden, T. M., & Song, D. (1994). Environmental quality and development: is there a Kuznets curve for air pollution emissions? *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 27(2), 147–162.
- (26) Shafik, N., & Bandyopadhyay, S. (1992). *Economic growth and environmental quality: time-series and cross-country evidence* (Vol. 904). World Bank Publications.
- (27) Shi, A. (2003). The impact of population pressure on global carbon dioxide emissions, 1975–1996: evidence from pooled cross-country data. *Ecological Economics*, 44(1), 29–42.
- (28) Wasti, S. K. A., & Zaidi, S. W. (2020). An empirical investigation between CO₂ emission,

energy consumption, trade liberalization and economic growth: A case of Kuwait. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 28, 101104.

(29) Watson, R. T., Zinyowera, M. C., & Moss, R. H. (1996). *Climate change 1995. Impacts, adaptations and mitigation of climate change: scientific-technical analyses*.